

A. Methodology of the Multivocal Literature Review

In this appendix, we report the details of the methodology adopted to conduct our MLR. We start by identifying a set of suitable search terms to compose an initial search query. We then refine our query by including keywords from a preliminary set of relevant search hits. Next, we employ the refined query to collect the search results from Google Search and Google Scholar, and we filter them according to our research objectives. We further expand our source set by applying the snowballing technique to the selected articles. Finally, we conduct a thematic analysis of the resulting corpus, extracting MLOps-related security risks and associated best practices. The following subsections report the whole process in detail.

A.1. Search Query Definition

A.1.1. Identification of the Search Terms

As a first step, we selected a set of suitable search terms for our MLR. We started by building an initial set of terms composed of words that we had already encountered in the literature, as well as their synonyms. Then, we sought additional search terms among the author-defined keywords from the preliminary search results. Lastly, we composed the final query.

A.1.2. Initial set of search terms

Our initial set of search terms is shown below. It mostly focused on matching the terms ‘MLOps’ and ‘machine learning’ (along with their synonyms and alternative spelling such as ‘model deployment’ and ‘ML’), with keywords commonly used to express security risks (e.g., ‘vulnerability,’ ‘threat’).

```
( "MLOps" OR "machine learning" OR "ML" OR "machine learning pipeline" OR "AI  
pipeline" OR "data pipeline" OR "model lifecycle" OR "model deployment" )  
AND  
( "security" OR "threat" OR "vulnerability" OR "risk" OR "cybersecurity" OR "attack" )
```

On Google Scholar, this query returned a total of 2.31M results, while on Google it returned 1.37M results.

To improve our search query and reduce the probability of missing relevant search hits, we analyzed the author-defined keywords listed in the first 100 Google Scholar search results.

A.1.3. Refinement of the search terms

To narrow down the results space while also ensuring that all relevant search terms are included in our query, following the example defined in [38], we planned to iteratively search for relevant author-defined keywords in academic articles.

We conducted an initial search in the Google Scholar database using the selected search terms. Next, we examined each search result and identified relevant results by inspecting the titles of the articles and, in case of any doubt, their abstracts. Lastly, we retrieved author-defined keywords from the subset of relevant hits and looked for repeated keywords (those that appeared

Figure 1: Infographic summarizing the data collection process for the MLR on MLOps security.

at least twice). We ensured filtering overly vague (e.g., ‘continuous monitoring’), vendor-specific (e.g., ‘Kubeflow’), or conceptually unrelated (e.g., ‘AIOps’) keywords.

The search for additional keywords was carried out by adopting the same stopping criterion (see Sect. A.2.1) applied to the execution of the final refined query.

A.1.4. Definition of the final query

Since we were unable to add any new term after the first search round, we stopped the iterative keyword search process there and built the final query for our MLR:

```
( "MLOps" OR "MLSecOps" OR "SecMLOps" OR "machine learning" OR "ML" OR "machine learning pipeline" OR "AI pipeline" OR "data pipeline" OR "model lifecycle" OR "model deployment" )
AND
( "security" OR "threat" OR "vulnerability" OR "risk" OR "cybersecurity" OR "attack" OR "SecOps" OR "DevSecOps" OR "SecDevOps" OR "protection" OR "safety" )
```

Note that the query shown here is a simplified version of the one used in our study; in the actual query, we explicitly included countable search terms in both their singular and plural form.

For the white literature, the final query execution returned 2.1M results in Google Scholar. For the gray literature, the final query execution returned 1.3M results in Google. When executing the new query, we checked the results pages for missing hits from the result sets returned by the initial query execution.

A.2. Data Collection

As mentioned earlier, to retrieve white literature (i.e., peer-reviewed scientific papers), we queried Google Scholar, as it indexes both large digital libraries such as IEEE Xplore and ACM Digital Library, and open-access archives such as ArXiv. Thus, we ensured to include in our search a broad range of scientific publication types (e.g., books or papers published in journals, conference proceedings, and technical magazines), as well as self-archived preprints. Instead, to retrieve gray literature, we performed a generic web search using Google.

Details on the number of search results retrieved from each query execution are reported in Figure 1. The initial analysis phases returned 60 potentially interesting results, based on the analysis of title, abstract, and keywords.

A.2.1. Stopping criterion

Given that the numbers of results returned by both the initial and final queries were still too large to ensure the analysis of each entry returned, we defined a reasonable ‘stopping criterion’. Accordingly, we decided to stop the analysis of results (both white and gray) after analyzing 5 consecutive pages of nonrelevant results.

The Google Scholar search (white literature) returned an extensive number of results (2.1M). We checked the relevance of about 310 hits (by reading the titles and abstracts) and stopped at the 31st page after inspecting five consecutive pages of unrelated results, as per the criterion defined above.

The search on Google (gray literature) also returned an extensive number of results (1.3M). We checked the relevance of about 170 hits and stopped at the 24th page after inspecting five consecutive pages of unrelated results.

A.2.2. Selection criteria

The selection and exclusion criteria that we used to decide whether to accept each search result are summarized in Table 3, along with their rationale.

We included search results that contain security risks and best practices to handle them in the context of MLOps. We decided to keep only search results consisting of articles, technical papers, PhD theses, or blog posts written in English, and exclude other kinds of multimedia (e.g., podcasts, product release notes, CVE). The language limitation is motivated by the consideration that high-quality research is generally published in English [38]. No date filtering was applied in our searches.

We also excluded search results that were found to be off topic after an in-depth read and those merely containing high-level, general-purpose information about securing the MLOps pipeline. Instead, we retained results containing actionable insights or takeaways for securing an ML pipeline.

The application of the filtering criteria described so far to the search results retrieved from each search engine left us with a corpus of 13 articles.

Table 3

List of inclusion and exclusion criteria applied to filter search results in the MLR on MLOps security.

Search results inclusion criterion	
The search result contains specific recommendations or take-away points for securing an ML pipeline.	
Search results exclusion criteria	
Criterion	Rationale
The article is not written in the English language.	-
The search result is not an article, book, a research/technical paper, or a blog post (e.g., podcast, commercial product release announcement, CVE).	-
The article is off-topic.	Does not contain information specific to the ML-enabled software development lifecycle.
The article only contains high-level, general-purpose pieces of information.	There are no recommendations or take-away points for securing an ML pipeline specifically.
The document is not available.	-

A.2.3. Snowballing

Given the low number of selected papers, we used the snowballing technique to find additional academic articles that we might have missed during the automated search. In particular, we engaged in the backward and forward snowballing process [23] leveraging, respectively, the references within and the citations of the selected white literature.

Our start set included the only academic paper selected. We did not retrieve any new article with the backward snowballing strategy, despite the high number of references contained. Also forward snowballing returned no further results as the selected paper has only been recently published in 2023. This was the last step of our data collection process, which is visually summarized in Figure 1.

The list of resources collected at the end of the collection process is presented in Table 4.

A.3. Data Extraction & Analysis

After carefully reading each of the selected articles, we extracted excerpts from the recommendations given and collected a raw catalog of security risks and best practices related to MLOps. By ‘best practice,’ we specifically mean an optimal behavior that can be adopted to improve a security-related aspect of MLOps activities.

To further refine our catalog, we collaboratively performed a thematic analysis of the raw collection of best practices and security risks [37]. In particular, we assigned a set of open codes to each best-practice and security risk, and, upon consolidation of the code set, we performed a final step of focused coding. With each code, we tried to summarize a set of excerpts containing similar risks/recommendations; therefore, the codes themselves can be read as high-level elements. Moreover, for each identified code, we noted down its support (i.e., the number of sources in which we observed it).

Table 4

Results matching the inclusion criteria for the multivocal literature review focusing on security in MLOps.

Search engine	ID	Result
Google	[G1]	[24]. Network security checklist for MLOps solutions. Azure Architecture Center.
Google	[G2]	[25]. Top 7 Layers of MLOps Security Advanced Guide
Google	[G3]	[26]. "MLOps security best practices"
Google	[G4]	[27]. As MLOps Hits Maturity it's Time to Consider Cybersecurity
Google	[G5]	[28]. Why cybersecurity is critical in MLOps
Google	[G6]	[29]. 7 layers of MLOps security
Google	[G7]	[30]. Five biggest risks of AI and Machine Learning that MLOps platforms help to address
Google	[G8]	[31]. Infusing Security into MLOps
Google	[G9]	[32]. The Importance of Secure Development in MLOps
Google	[G10]	[33]. MLSecOps: Defined
Google	[G11]	[34]. Adopting MLSecOps: Securing Machine Learning at Scale
Google	[G12]	[35]. Adopting MLSecOps for secure machine learning at scale
Google Scholar	[W1]	[36]. Conceptualizing the Secure Machine Learning Operations (SecMLOps) Paradigm